

Effect of stress management techniques on employee Job performance in manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Tojue Obianuju Grace ¹, Audu Omeiza Leonard ² and Nnamani John Nnaemeka ^{3,*}

¹ Department of Management, University of Nigeria Enugu Campus, Nigeria.

² Department of Business Administration and Management, Federal Polytechnic Nasarawa, Nigeria.

³ Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Nigeria.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(02), 449–461

Publication history: Received on 28 March 2023; revised on 07 May 2023; accepted on 09 May 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.2.0817>

Abstract

The study examined the effect of stress management techniques on employee job performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the sought to: ascertain effect of meditation technique on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms and evaluate effect of relaxation technique on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms. The research design was descriptive survey methods. Study Area was Enugu State. Enugu State, South-East of Nigeria. The sample size of 378 respondents was drawn from the population of 657 employee of four manufacturing firms namely Nigeria Breweries 9th mile corner Enugu, Innoson technical and industrial company Ltd Emene Enugu, Juhel pharmaceutical company Emene Enugu, Aqua Rapha water company 9th mile Corner Enugu. Research questions of the study were answered using mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses stated were tested using regression analysis which comprises of t-statistic, f-statistic and correlation analysis. The empirical results show that meditation technique has significant effect on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Nigeria (t-statistics = 5.292; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005) and relaxation technique has significant effect on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Nigeria (t-statistics = 6.491; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005). The study concluded that there was positive and significant effect of stress management techniques on performance of employee of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that: management of manufacturing firms in Nigeria should invest in the different stress dimension management strategy such as meditation technique and relaxation technique so as to improve employee performance.

Keywords: Meditation technique; Relaxation techniques; Stress management techniques

1. Introduction

Many employees in the course of discharging their duties in organizations experience one form of stress or the other. This is why Obi, (2020) opine that stress is a worldwide experience in the lives of many employees. Similarly, Odita, (2023) posits that stress is inevitable in a work environment. Some of the underlying theories and underpinning concepts behind stress are now settled and accepted; others are still being researched and debated. Stress is changing to a common phenomenon among employers and employees. Employees experience and feel stressed continuously and therefore the reactions of stress at the workplace are not a separate aspect. But considering stress more positively leads to higher productivity and improved performance, whereas, negative stress leads to many problems in the organization. Hence, it is pertinent for organizations to take cognizance of the stress level of their employees and make an attempt to help them overcome it (Syed, Muhammad, Aftab Qadir & Shabana, 2013).

* Corresponding author: Nnamani John Nnaemeka

According to Gibbons (2021), workplace pressures inhibit employee performance regardless of organisation type. Tight deadlines, insufficient time off, low morale, too much work, and bad tech innovation. Poor organisational culture (Oditia, 2021); excessive job content and demands; role conflict and ambiguity; debauched management practise; uncomfortable working environment (physical and psychological); distress; terrible workplace relationships; etc (Better Health Channel, 2020). Heavy workload, excessive job demands, organisational change, career and job ambiguity, lack of recognition, and harassment are major workplace stressors. Tamunomiebi and Mezeh (2021) categorised workplace stressors as psychological, psychosocial, role overload, role limits, culture integration, and job demand.

Stress management technique is a set of strategies and programmes designed to assist people handle stress at work by identifying stressors and reducing their impact (Gale Encyclopedia of Medicine, as cited in Brown, 2021). It's a "broad range of methods and psychotherapies focused at regulating a person's stress, usually to improve everyday function" (Oditia, 2023). Stress management consists of elements/components that must be used properly to operate efficiently at work. They include cognitive-behavioral, meditation technique, relaxation technique, mind-body, and time-management practises (Turcotte& Sanders, 2014). Brown (2021) categorised stress-management strategies as action-oriented, emotional, and acceptance-oriented. 'Coping competence' (Moller, 2016) and 'social support' are further stress management characteristics (World Health Organization [W.H.O.], 2020). All these solutions show that workers may lessen or adapt to job stress. Thus, workplace stress can be handled and controlled, justifying the concept of "coping competence" (Gofen, 2014; Moller, 2016). It is already a known fact that there is the possibility for a worker to encounter stress situations at their workplaces. It therefore becomes imperative to find out if there is an influence existing in the different dimensions of stress management techniques highlighted in this background on employee job performance at the workplace.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian manufacturing industry has experienced tremendous growth and changes over the past few years. Most organizations, to accomplish higher productivity, end up saddling employees with an overload of work to meet deadlines, and this might have psychological and physical effects on the employees which may result in something contrary to what these organizations want to achieve.

Work stress arises from stressors in the workplace. These stressors are demanding and unreasonable situations associated with the organization itself. They include high levels of organizational politics, demanding organizational cultures and poor leadership styles which can create friction; heighten dysfunctional competition between individuals and increased stress (Manjunatha & Renukamurthy, 2017). Lack of performance feedback, inadequate career development, workplace violence, sexual harassment and inequality in remuneration and incentives have also been cited as some of the causes of the increase in stress among employees (Orji and Makubu, 2020). While these organizations are devising stress coping mechanisms and management strategies to curb the situation and are becoming more aware of the effects of work-related stress, the same cannot be said about the organizations in developing countries like Nigeria especially the manufacturing sector.

Although, several empirical studies have been conducted in Nigeria on the relation between job-related stress and the performance of workers, very little or none have been done on how these workers cope with these situations or on how they can deal with the issues caused by these stressors at the workplace. After going through empirical literature only because of this study, no documented evidence abound on the effect of stress management techniques. However, this study seeks to investigate the dimension of workplace management strategies bothering on meditation technique and relaxation technique on employee job performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria, hence, the need for this study. These strategies have not been adequately addressed by previous studies and the current study seeks to address the lacuna.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effect of stress management techniques on employee job performance in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- Ascertain effect of meditation technique on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- Evaluate effect of relaxation technique on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial and important the following of groups namely management of manufacturing firms in Nigeria and employees of the organizations. The study is of immense significance to managers who wish to be effective in management of employees who are facing stress problems at their workplace. They therefore need to have at least a basic understanding of on how employees who are in stress challenges can be managed.

The outcome of the study will ultimately benefit employees when they are made to explore the stressors that are present in their own work environment, and take steps to reduce and/or prevent stress in the workplace, thereby working to maintain their health and well-being.

2. Conceptual Literature

2.1. Workplace Stress

The term stress has been defined by many scholars. Stress represents a situation where a person is under pressure and does not have sufficient ability to cope with it. Jayashree (2010) cited in Orji and Makubu, (2020) perceive stress as a physical or emotional factor that causes bodily or mental tension, and maybe a factor in disease causation. Chandra and Sudesh, (2022) defines stress as a chronic complex emotional state with apprehension and is characteristic of various nervous and mental disorders. In essence, stress is a manifest response of an individual to defiling the basic needs of life in an environment of competing needs. It is a person's psychological and physiological response to the perception of demand and challenge. Work-related stress is a pattern of physiological, emotional, cognitive and behavioural reactions to some extreme taxing aspects of work content, work organization and work environment (Biriowu & Chikwe, 2019).

Sucharitha and Shaik, (2020) opine that stress is a change in one's physical or mental state, in other words, disturbance or imbalance from a normal state. Stress is caused by disturbing events in a work environment, social environment, and in routine life (work, family and social life) and also caused by emotional, psychological, mental and physical illness. Moreover, "Stress comes from any situation or circumstance that requires behavioural adjustment.

2.2. Stress management techniques

Sucharitha and Shaik, (2020) defines stress management as the proactive measures that individuals and organizations put in place to deal with stress before it affects employees. This therefore means that stress management is dealing with possible stressors before they become stress to organizational employees at individual level or at a group level. There are several variables of stress management phenomenon including work place counselling. Stress management as Petreanu, Lordache and Seracin, (2020) observes is a wide area of techniques that focuses on ways in which stress can be mitigated in organizations of all sizes so as to minimize the negative outcomes of stress. Stress management therefore manifest in different ways depending on one organization to another. According to Orji and Makubu, (2020) the manifestation of stress management can be in terms of flexible work schedule, work place counseling or even work place quality since such constructs, upon proper implementation may reduce stress. On the other hand, Manjunatha and Renukamurthy, (2017) opines that stress management is entirely dependent on individual organization and techniques used are not universally standardized.

2.3. Employee Job Performance

Assibey-Ankrah, (2021) opined that employee performance is an action what employees do in carrying out the work done by the company. Performance in carrying out its functions is not independent, but always relates to employee job satisfaction and the level of reward given, and influenced by individual skills, abilities, and traits. Employee job performance means work performance or actual achievement achieved by an employee. Employee job performance is the work quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his function in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Employee job performance refers to the degree of employee's achievement of the goal as well as the range of measurements of efficiency in workplaces. In general, employee performance is indicated by data that represents effectiveness such as productivity, goal achievement levels, customer satisfaction index, and attachment (Orji & Makubu, (2020). In the view of Kihara and Mugambi, (2018), employee performance focuses directly on employee productivity by assessing the number of units of acceptable quality produced by an employee, within a specific time period. The success of business or an organization depends on employees' performance.

2.4. Contextual Literature

2.4.1. Meditation Techniques

Stress occurs when you perceive that demands placed on you such as work, school or relations exceed your ability to cope. Untreated chronic stress can result in serious health conditions including anxiety, insomnia, muscle pain, high blood pressure and a weakened immune system.

Research shows that stress can contribute to the development of major illnesses such as heart disease, depression and obesity. But finding positive, healthy ways to manage stress as it occurs, many of these negative health consequences can be reduced such as meditation. Meditation and mindful prayer help the mind and body to relax and focus. Mindfulness can help people see new perspective, develop self-compassion and forgiveness. When practicing a form of mindfulness, people can release emotions that may have been causing like exercise. Research has shown that even meditating briefly can reap immediate benefits (Yeboah-Kordee, Amponsah-Tawiah, Adu, & Ashie, 2018).

Altindag, (2020) in the study on “Effects on Psychological Symptomatology, Sense of Control and Spiritual Experiences”, the study examined the effects of an eight (8) week stress reduction program based on training in mindfulness meditation. Previous research efforts suggesting this program may be beneficial in terms of reducing stress-related symptomatology and helping patients cope with chronic pain have been limited by a lack of adequate comparison control groups. Twenty eight individuals who volunteered to participate in the present study were randomized into either an experimental group or a nonintervention control group. The study concluded that the techniques of mindfulness meditation, with their emphasis in developing detached observation and awareness of contents of consciousness may represent a powerful cognitive behavioral coping strategy for transforming the ways in which we respond to stressful life events. They may also have potential for relapse prevention in effective disorder (Altindag, 2020).

2.4.2. Relaxation Techniques

Relaxation techniques are a great way to help with stress management. Relaxation is not just about peace of mind or enjoying a hobby but it is a process that decreases the effects of stress on your mind and body. Relaxation techniques can help you cope with everyday stress and with stress related to various health problems, such as cancer and pain (Mayo Clinic, 2016). Relaxation techniques can reduce stress symptoms and help an individual enjoy a better quality of life especially if one has an illness. Practicing relaxation techniques can reduce stress symptoms by slowing the heart rate, lowering blood pressure, slowing breathing rate, reducing activity of stress hormones, increasing blood flow to major muscles, reducing muscles tension and chronic pain, improving concentration and mind, lowering fatigue, reducing anger and frustration and boosting confidence to handle problems. Assibey-Ankrah, (2021) opined that relaxation plays a vital role in curbing stress. In a state of great or deep relaxation, the employee is physically relaxed and detached from the stress-causing situation. Relaxation exercises reduce the employee’s heart rates, blood pressure and other indicators of stress. Another way to ease stress individually is opening to someone. This involves confiding in a trusted person a personal crisis. The act of confiding is a big sigh of relief to the employee. This self-disclosure goes a long way to reduce stress and give a more positive outlook on life.

In the study on “Stress Management in Work Settings”, a variety of stress management techniques was used in worksite studies, including muscle relaxation, meditation, biofeedback, cognitive-behavioral skills and combinations of these techniques. The most common techniques used were muscle relaxation, cognitive-behavioral skills and combinations of two or more techniques. The study concluded that the large number of different stress management techniques coupled with the wide range of health outcome measures used in stress intervention studies makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions about the efficacy of each technique and each outcome (Petreanu, Lordache & Seracin, 2020).

In a study titled “Effects of Occupational Stress Management Intervention Program” meta-analysis was conducted to determine the effectiveness of stress management interventions in occupational settings. Thirty six experimental studies were included, representing 55 interventions. Total sample size was 2,847. Of the participants, 59% were female, mean age was 35.4, and average length of intervention was 7.4 weeks. The interventions were coded as cognitive-behavioral, relaxation organizational, multimodal or alternative. Within the sample of studies, relaxations interventions were most frequently used, and organizational interventions continued to be scarce (Chandra & Sudesh, 2022).

2.5. Theoretical Foundation of the Study

2.5.1. Adlerian Theory on Counselling

Alfred Adler believed that human behavior is goal oriented and that humans can best be understood in terms of how they go about trying to achieve their goals. A person's unique lifestyle determines how they work towards their goals throughout their life. Adler believes emotional and psychological problems which cause stress occur because of mistaken lifestyle, about how to achieve life goals and these interferes with a person's ability to function and successfully achieve his goals (Evans & John, 2013). Counselling involves forming an effective relationship and assessing a person's lifestyle, particularly regarding mistaken beliefs. A client gains insight into the mistaken beliefs during the lifestyle assessment, and the therapist encourages the clients towards reorientation and change. Encouragement is a major therapeutic technique to manage stress and therefore improve on performance (Pearson Education, 2010).

2.5.2. Cognitive Theory of Psychological Stress and Coping

Lazarus and Folkman's theory of psychological stress and coping is perhaps the most theoretically influential transactional theory. Sometimes known as the Cognitive-Relational approach, the individual and their environment are seen as coexisting in a dynamic relationship, where stress is the psychological and emotional state that is internally represented as part of a stressful transaction (Mark & Smith, 2010). Once possible coping methods are assessed and selected, then the final stage of the mode occurs, where coping is implemented. Coping has been characterized as cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage, reduce, minimize, master or tolerate the internal and external demands of the person-environmental transaction that is appraised as taxing or exceeding the person's resources. The cognitive-relational model gives weight to the job situation, subjective perceptions, and the potential influence or various individual differences factors and indeed Lazarus argues that many stress management interventions fail because they treat all people as if they were alike, and it is useful to view the individual, the group and the workplace as a single analytic unit, rather than separate variables which are to be manipulated independently.

2.5.3. Empirical Review

Odita, (2023) examined stress management strategies and employee performance in manufacturing firms in Edo State. The specific objectives were to: identify the relationship among workplace social support, coping competence, time management techniques, mind-body techniques and employee's performance. Sample size of 301 respondents was drawn from 1663 population staff of selected manufacturing firms. The data analytical technique were both descriptive and Pearson's and Spearman's rank correlation statistics. Empirical results show that employees in manufacturing firms receive maximum workplace social support and this helps them deal with stressful work situations; and they have high coping competence in handling stress. Also, it was revealed that time management was the most adopted stress management strategy among workers in manufacturing firms and they practice it to a high extent. In addition, it was discovered that mind-body strategy of time management is adopted by the employees, although, not to a very high extent when compared with their adoption of other stress management techniques. The study recommended that the management of manufacturing firms should sensitize their employees in understanding the benefits of mind-body interventions such as massage, yoga, etc. and how to make good use of them for reducing stress levels.

Chandra and Sudesh, (2022) conducted a study to investigate the effect of workplace stress management techniques on employees' efficiency in banking industrial in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to examine chronic stress, traumatic stress and acute stress on employee performance in the banking sector in Nigeria. The data analytical technique was regression statistics. The sample size of 79 employees was drawn from a total of 105 population in selected banks. The results indicate that stress program interventions and training and development have a significant influence on employees' efficiency. The study recommends that Bank managers in Nigeria should ensure that employees receive the necessary instructions, guidelines, and policies that clearly define their work roles, with no contradictions or ambiguity to warrant ambiguity in job execution.

Assibey-Ankrah, (2021) sought to examine the effect of stress management practices on employee performance at the University of Cape Coast, Ghana. The specific objectives that guided the study were; to assess the various stress management practices; to assess employee performance; and to examine the effect of stress management practices on employee performance. The population of the study was 923 administrative staff and the sample size of 269. The main instrument used for this study was a structured questionnaire with statistical tools including; mean, standard deviation (SD), frequencies, percentages and linear regression analysis. The study findings first indicated that psychological support, training and development, job redesign and employee welfare programmes were the various stress management practices at the University of Cape Coast. The study also revealed that there is a significant and strong positive relationship between stress management practices and employee performance. The study recommended that

management of the University should practice a combination of all the practices of stress management discovered in this study in combating stress.

Obi, (2020) examined the effect of stress on employee productivity in selected manufacturing firms in South-East Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to identify the relationship among work-family interaction, organizational climate, role ambiguity and employee productivity. The population of the study consisted of 2187 employees of fifteen selected manufacturing firms. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973) was employed to determine the sample size of 427. The data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression analysis at a 5% level of significance. The results showed that work-family interaction exerts a significant negative influence on employee productivity, organizational climate has a significant positive effect on employee productivity, while role ambiguity has a significant positive influence on employee productivity. The study, therefore, concluded that workplace stress has a significant negative effect on employee productivity in manufacturing firms in South-East Nigeria. The study among other things recommended that management should encourage employees to spend time with their family and that they should be allowed to go home at a reasonable time to meet their family in order to avoid work family-related stress.

Abonyo, (2020) conducted a study to investigate the effect of stress management on employee performance at Kenya Airways. Specifically, the study sought to examine the effect of flexible work schedule, work place counseling and work place quality on employee performance at Kenya Airways. The mean and standard deviation were used to present data while data analytical techniques were regression and correlation method. The study found out that stress management explains variation of employee performance. Additionally, the research established that flexible work schedule had significant positive correlation with employee performance; work place counseling had insignificant negative correlation with employee performance and that work place quality had a significant positive relationship with employee performance. The study concluded that both work place quality and flexible work scheduling have roles to play in employee performance but not work place counseling. The study recommended policy and practice should include work place quality and flexible work schedule to enhance employee performance.

Biriowu and Chikwe, (2019) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of stress management techniques and organizational performance in selected private and public Hospitals in Port Harcourt. The specific objectives of the study were to examine the extent of the influence of stress management techniques on organizational performance and investigate into the extent of relationship between flexible working hour and organizational performance. A total of 120 statistically selected respondents were derived from 30 statistically selected private and public hospitals in Port Harcourt. The methods of data analysis were Pearson's correlation and multiple regression techniques. The study revealed that severe stress is psychologically hazardous, mentally harmful and impacts negatively on organizational performance. Moderate stress as revealed tends to be potentially useful in organizational performance. The study recommended that maintenance of appropriate job design and flexible working hour policies, amongst others in respective functional areas.

Kihara and Mugambi, (2018) evaluated the influence of stress management techniques on employees' performance of Public Service in Kenya. Specifically, the study sought to examine effect of counseling services strategies, flextime programme strategies, mediation technique strategies, and relaxation technique strategies on employees' performance. Descriptive research design was adopted. The sample size of 400 employee of public service was drawn from 700,000 target population of the study. Data analytical technique was mean, standard deviation and single regression method. The results show that there is significant effect on employees' performance of Public Service, explained by a 91.1% variation. The regression model also indicated that there was a positive relationship between employees' performance and the factor variables studies of relaxation techniques and counselling services. The study recommended that the management of the organization under study should create awareness to the employees to enable them be aware of utilization of stress management techniques available in the organization that can result in improved performance.

3. Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey methods. Study Area was Enugu State. Enugu State, South-East of Nigeria. The sample size of 378 respondents was drawn from the population of 657 employee of four manufacturing firms namely Nigeria Breweries 9th mile corner Enugu, Innoson technical and industrial company Ltd Emene Enugu, Juhel pharmaceutical company Emene Enugu, Aqua Rapha water company 9th mile Corner Enugu. Research questions of the study were answered using mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses stated were tested using regression analysis which comprises of t-statistic, f-statistic and correlation analysis.

3.1. Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 1 Comprehensive Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Title	Frequency	Percentage
Questionnaire Distributed	378	100%
Returned Questionnaire	358	95%
Not Returned Questionnaire	20	5%
Gender		
Female	213	59.5%
Male	145	40.5%
Age Bracket		
20-30 years	153	42.7%
31-40 years	111	31.0%
41-50 years	66	18.4%
51 Years and above	28	7.8%
Educational Qualification		
NCE/ND	9	10.0%
HND/B.sc	193	53.9%
MBA/M.Sc	125	34.9%
Ph.D	2	1.2%
Work Experience		
1-5 Years	111	31.0%
6-10 Years	153	42.7%
11-20 Years	66	18.4%
21-35 Years	28	7.8%

Sources: Field Survey, 2023

Three hundred and seventy eight (378) copies of questionnaire were designed and distributed to the respondents. Out of the 378 Questionnaires distributed, 358 (95%) were completed and returned while 20 (5%) were not returned. Therefore, 95 percent respondents were a good representation. The table showed the respondents profile in frequency and percentage distribution of gender, age bracket, educational qualification, and working experience.

3.2. Data Analysis

3.2.1. Question One

What is the extent to which meditation technique affects employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria?

This table showed the opinion of respondents on the extent to which meditation technique affects employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria. The research items 1,2,3,4 have mean score of above 4.0 point respectively and it was rated great extent by respondents. The study thereby revealed that meditation technique has significant effect on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria since meditation enables employees to have reflection time that bring peace thus reducing stress (The grand mean 4.255 was greater than the cutoff point 3).

Table 2 Mean rating of responses of respondents on the extent to which meditation technique affects employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria

S/N	Question Items	VGE (5)	GE (4)	ME (3)	LE (2)	VLE (1)	Total	Mean	SD
1	Meditation helps employees to be more peaceful, more focused and less worried when practiced	900	400	144	46	7	1497	4.18	0.0030
		180	100	48	23	7	358		
		50%	30%	13%	6%	1%	100%		
2	Meditation enables employees to have reflection time that bring peace thus reducing stress	630	632	192	40	10	1504	4.20	0.0030
		126	158	64	20	10	358		
		35%	44%	18%	5%	2%	100%		
3	It helps employees become focused in planning work and reduces work pressure and increases concentration	1000	404	135	18	3	1560	4.36	0.0033
		200	101	45	9	3	358		
		59%	28%	13%	2%	0.8%	100%		
4	Meditation helps employees to cool their nerves in disturbing occurrence and help to review and analyses situation which brings stress and avoid them	950	444	105	24	10	1533	4.28	0.0032
		190	111	35	12	10	358		
		53%	31%	9%	3%	2%	100%		
	Grand Mean							4.255	0.0031

Source: Field Survey, 2023

3.2.2. Question Two

What is the extent to which relaxation technique affects employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria?

Table 3 Mean rating of responses of respondents on the extent to which relaxation technique affects employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria

S/N	Question Items	VGE (5)	GE (4)	ME (3)	LE (2)	VLE (1)	Total	Mean	SD
1	Practicing relaxation techniques can reduce stress symptoms by slowing the heart rate, lowering blood pressure, slowing breathing rate, reducing activity of stress hormones, increasing blood flow to major muscles	630	632	192	40	10	1504	4.20	0.0030
		126	158	64	20	10	358		
		35%	44%	18%	5%	2%	100%		
2	Relief from work techniques can help you cope with everyday stress and with stress related to various health problems, such as cancer	580	632	222	26	17	1477	4.13	0.0029
		116	158	74	13	17	358		
		32%	44%	21%	3%	2%	100%		
3	Reduction in strictness reduces stress symptoms and help an individual enjoy a better quality of life especially if one has an illness.	900	400	144	46	7	1497	4.18	0.0030
		180	100	48	23	7	358		
		50%	30%	13%	6%	1%	100%		
4	Practicing relaxation techniques increasing blood flow to major muscles,	985	416	111	24	8	1544	4.31	0.0032
		197	104	37	12	8	358		

	reducing muscles tension and chronic pain, improving concentration and mind, reducing anger and frustration and boosting confidence to handle problems.	55%	29%	10%	3%	2%	100%		
	Grand Mean							4.205	0.0030

Source: Field Survey, 2023

This table showed the opinion of respondents on what is the extent to which relaxation technique affects employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria. The research items 1,2,3,4 have mean score of above 4.0 point respectively and it was rated great extent by respondents. The study thereby revealed that relaxation technique has significant effect on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria since practicing relaxation techniques increasing blood flow to major muscles, reducing muscles tension and chronic pain, improving concentration and mind, reducing anger and frustration and boosting confidence to handle problems. (The grand me 4.205 was greater than the cutoff point 3).

4. Test of Hypotheses

4.1. Test of Hypothesis Two

H_0 = Meditation technique has no significant effect on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria.

Table 4 Regression Results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.941 ^a	0.885	0.884	0.34657
a. Predictors: (Constant), Meditation technique				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	323.116	1	323.116	7.409	0.000 ^b
	Residual	1113.840	357	3.120		
	Total	1436.956	358			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee effectiveness; b. Predictors: (Constant), Meditation technique

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.195	0.086		2.275	0.024
	Meditation technique	0.206	0.039	0.941	5.292	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee effectiveness

In testing this hypothesis, meditation technique was regressed against employee effectiveness. The result of the single-regression analysis showed the model to ascertain effect of meditation technique on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria.

4.2. Employee effectiveness = 0.195 + 0.206 Meditation strategies

The empirical result showed that the coefficient of meditation strategy has positive effect on employee effectiveness; it means that fringe benefits reward has positive and direct effect on employee effectiveness. The result of the t – statistics denotes that the coefficient of meditation technique was statistically significance because the observed values of t – statistics (5.292) was greater than its p-values (0.000). The result of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression of the hypothesis one was statistically significance because the observed value of the F – statistics (7.409) was great than its p-value (0.000). Again, our empirical result showed that the Pearson product moment correlation analysis (r) was 0.941. The strength of relationship between the two variables was high. However, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that meditation technique has positive and significant effect on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria (t-statistics = 5.292; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005).

4.3. Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀ = Relaxation technique has no significant effect on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria.

Table 5 Regression Results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.917 ^a	0.840	0.810	0.40781
a. Predictors: (Constant), Relaxation technique				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.016	1	22.016	6.954	0.000 ^b
	Residual	1130.262	357	3.166		
	Total	1152.278	358			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee job satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Relaxation technique						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.650	0.113		5.645	0.000
	Photocopy machine	0.391	0.062	0.917	6.312	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Quality job delivery						

In testing this hypothesis, relaxation technique was regressed against employee job satisfaction. The result of the single-regression analysis showed the model to evaluate effect of relaxation technique on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria.

4.4. Employee job satisfaction = 0.650 + 0.233 Relaxation technique

The empirical result showed that the coefficient of relaxation technique has positive effect on employee job satisfaction; it means that relaxation technique has positive and direct effect on employee job satisfaction. The result of the t –

statistics denotes that the coefficient of relaxation technique was statistically significance because the observed values of t – statistics (9.312) is greater than its P-values (0.000). The result of the F – statistical test showed that the overall regression of the hypothesis one was statistically significance because the observed value of the F – statistics (6.954) was great than its P-value (0.000). Again, our empirical result showed that the Pearson product moment correlation analysis (r) was 0.917. The strength of relationship between the two variables was high. However, we rejected the null hypothesis and conclude that relaxation technique has positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria (t-statistics = 6.491; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005).

Summary of the Findings

The following are the major findings of the study:

- The study revealed that meditation technique has significant effect on employee effectiveness of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria since meditation enables employees to have reflection time that bring peace thus reducing stress (t-statistics = 5.292; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005).
- The study revealed that relaxation technique has significant effect on employee job satisfaction of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria since practicing relaxation technique increasing blood flow to major muscles, reducing muscles tension and chronic pain, improving concentration and mind, reducing anger and frustration and boosting confidence to handle problems (t-statistics = 6.491; P-value = 0.000 < Sig-value 0.005).

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that there was positive and significant effect of stress management techniques on performance of employee of manufacturing firms in Enugu State Nigeria. The study identify that major stress management techniques are meditation technique and relaxation technique. Meditation helps employees to be more peaceful, more focused and less worried when practiced, meditation enables employees to have reflection time that bring peace thus reducing stress, it helps employees become focused in planning work and reduces work pressure and increases concentration and meditation helps employees to cool their nerves in disturbing occurrence and help to review and analyses situation which brings stress and avoid them. Practicing relaxation techniques can reduce stress symptoms by slowing the heart rate, lowering blood pressure, slowing breathing rate, reducing activity of stress hormones, increasing blood flow to major muscles, Relief from work techniques can help you cope with everyday stress and with stress related to various health problems, such as cancer, reduction in strictness reduces stress symptoms and help an individual enjoy a better quality of life especially if one has an illness and practicing relaxation techniques increasing blood flow to major muscles, reducing muscles tension and chronic pain, improving concentration and mind, reducing anger and frustration and boosting confidence to handle problems.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- Management of manufacturing firms should invest in the different stress dimension management strategy such as meditation technique and relaxation technique so as to improve employee performance. The management of the studied firms needs to establish a policy that will have good role clarity plans, which can relieve the employees from the future role ambiguity.
- Management of manufacturing firms should invest in stress management practices such as stress management training, seminars on job burnouts, supportive organisational climate, yoga and meditation, the close association of co-workers, celebrations are practised periodically at the executive level. But, celebration, stress management training and yoga and meditation are the most preferred practices.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We give all thanks to God Almighty for the academic wisdom.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest among the authors.

References

- [1] Abonyo, B.A. (2020) Stress management and employee performance at Kenya Airways; Master Dissertation, Department of Business Administration in Human Resource, School of Business, University of Nairobi Kenya.
- [2] Altindag, O. (2020). Relationship between stress management and job performance in organizations. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 9(2), 43-49.
- [3] Assibey-Ankrah, F. (2021) Stress management practices and employees' performance at the University of Cape Coast; MBA Dissertation, Department of Business Administration; University of Cape Coast.
- [4] Bennett, K., & Dorjee, D. (2016). The impact of a Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Course (MBSR) on well-being and academic attainment of sixth-form students. *Mindfulness*, 7(1), 105–114.
- [5] Biriowu, C. S. and Chikwe, J. E. (2019) Stress management techniques and organizational performance in selected private and public Hospitals in Port Harcourt, Nigeria; *International Journal of Business Management and Research*; 9 (6), 27–36.
- [6] Brown, A. (2021). 62 stress management techniques, strategies & activities. Retrieved from <https://positivepsychology.com/stress-management-techniques-tips-burn-out/#techniques-stress-management>
- [7] Chandra, S. P. and Sudesh, K. K. (2022) Effect of Workplace Stress management techniques on Employees' Efficiency; *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*; 7 (7); 12-23.
- [8] Chandra, S.P. and Sudesh, K.K. (2019). Effect of Workplace Stress Management Strategies on Employees' Efficiency. *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research* 4(5):412-418.
- [9] Cheung, I. O. L. (2016). An exploration of the stressors and coping factors of parents of children with autism spectrum disorder, with focus in the impact of Christian faith and implications for local churches. Biola University.
- [10] Gibbons, S. (2021). 5 stressors in your workplace and how to deal with them. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/serenitygibbons/2021/02/18/5-stressors-in-your-workplace-and-how-to-deal-with-them/?sh=79720e8150b8>
- [11] Gofen, A. (2014). Mind the gap: Dimensions and influence of street-level divergence. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 24, 473-493.
- [12] Jayashree, R. (2010). Stress management with special reference to public sector bank employees in Chennai. *International Journal of Enterprise and Innovation Management Studies (IJEIMS)*, 1(3), 34- 35.
- [13] Kihara, L. N. and Mugambi, H. (2018) Effect of stress management techniques on employees' performance in the public service; *Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management*; 5 (2); 2382 – 2405.
- [14] Manjunatha, M. K., & Renukamurthy, T. P. (2017). Stress among banking employee-A literature review. *Int. J. Res. Granthaalayah*, 5, 207-213
- [15] Obi, N. C. (2020) Stress and Employee Productivity in Selected Manufacturing Firms in South-East Nigeria; *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science*; 5 (12); 54-69.
- [16] Odita, A. O. (2023) Stress Management Strategies and Employee Performance: An Application of Correlational Research Design on Manufacturing Firms in Edo State, Nigeria; *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*; 6 (2); 678-690.
- [17] Orji, M.G and Makubu, G.N. (2020) Effective Stress Management and Employee Productivity in the Nigerian Public Institutions; A Study of National Gallery of Arts, Abuja, Nigeria; *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal* 3 (2): 1303-1315
- [18] Pearson Education. (2010). Adlerian Counseling. Retrieved November 28, 2016, from <http://wps.prenhall.com/chet archer theories 1/47/12099/3097511.cw/index.html>
- [19] Petreanu, V., Lordache, R., & Seracin, M (2020). Assessment of work stress influence of work productivity in Romanian companies. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 92(2013): 420-425
- [20] Sucharitha, M.M. and Shaik, A. B. (2020) A Study on impact of stress on employee's productivity and job performance: implications for stress measurement and management; *Ilkogretim Online - Elementary Education*; 19 (4): 823-831

- [21] Syed, M. H. N., Muhammad, A. K., AftabQadir, K., &Shabana, N. K. (2013). Job Stress and Employees' Productivity: Case of Azad Kashmir Public Health Sector. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(3), 525 - 542.
- [22] Tamunomiebi, M. D., & Mezeh, A. A. (2021). Workplace stressors and employee performance: A conceptual review. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 21(4), 57-66.
- [23] Taylor, S. (1995). *Managing people at work*. London: Reed Educational and Professional Publishing Ltd.
- [24] Turcotte, C., & Sanders, M. J. (2014). Strategies for managing stress. Retrieved from <https://dimensionsofdentalhygiene.com/article/strategies-for-managing-stress/>
- [25] Wikipedia (2021). Stress management. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stress_management#Stress_management_programs
- [26] World Health Organization [W.H.O.], (2020). Occupational health: Stress at the workplace. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/q-a-detail/ccupational-health-stress-at-the-workplace>
- [27] Yang, F. C., Kao, R. H., & Cho, C. C. (2019). A multilevel study on the causal relationship in association network of work stress. *Policing: An International Journal*, 42(4), 624–639.
- [28] Yeboah-Kordee, N. S., Amponsah-Tawiah, K., Adu, I. N., &Ashie, A. A. (2018). An investigation of the impact of occupational stress on employee performance: Evidence from the Ghanaian Banking Sector. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(9), 150–169.